

A Random, Observational, Retrospective and Self-Reported Survey about Natural Contaminations of Heavy Metals in Food and SARS-Cov-2 Risks

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Based on reports from 1,000 families, by random, observational, retrospective and self-reported method, Families that have been naturally (but not intentionally) exposed to natural contaminants of heavy metals through food, One-sixth of other families' rate have experienced SARS-Cov-2 death (with 87% statistical certainty). Also, the relative risk of Apparent SARS-Cov-2 infection for them was 0.5 (100% statistical certainty). These results suggest that the natural presence of natural heavy metal contaminants in food or water could decrease the risk of SARS-Cov-2 Death (by one-sixth ratio).

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